

CIVIL RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS

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Annotation: The rights and obligations of participants in civil legal turnover are an integral part of the relations between them and are regulated by law. The basis for their occurrence is the legislation itself, the actions of legal entities, decisions of authorities, judicial decisions. The emergence of duties or rights provided for by law is associated with the occurrence of some events. For example, upon reaching the age stipulated by the law on military service, all male persons are subject to conscription into the armed forces.

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Rights and obligations tend to arise, change and terminate. Therefore, when a certain age comes, men cannot be called up for military service in peacetime, and when they reach another age limit, they drop out of the lists of military service and are not subject to conscription even if war breaks out.

However, the car only creates conditions for the right to own and use it as property to arise. At the heart of the emergence of the right is the will of the citizen, aimed at satisfying their needs. It is for this reason that he becomes a party to the purchase and sale transaction.

In turn, normative and legal grounds only create prerequisites for the dynamics of legal relations. Thus, the ownership of a car is a potential basis for the possibility of selling it, exchanging it, giving it away, putting it up as collateral for a transaction or using it. Otherwise, it is called prerequisites for the movement of legal communication.

The basis of the movement of civil and legal turnover are legal facts. It is the fact that a citizen is the owner of a car that gives rise to the right to make transactions in which the car will act as an object.

The law of obligations is clearly divided into a general part containing rules to be applied in regulating all types of obligations, and numerous institutions, each of which regulates certain types of obligations (purchase and sale, contract, bank relations with customers, transportation, and many others).

The next section of civil law covers the so-called non-contractual obligations (torts) generated by the actions of citizens or legal entities that cause damage to other citizens and legal entities outside of contractual relations with them.

According to the system adopted by us, torts are followed by an extensive section regulating relations related to the creation and use of the results of intellectual activity; that is, with the emergence and exercise of intellectual property rights. Legislation and applicable practice distinguish two subsections in this section: copyright, which regulates relations on the creation and use of works of science, literature and art, and patent law, which covers the use of the results of creative activity in industry and production. This subsection is often referred to as industrial law. It is adjoined by the norms on means of individualization of participants in civil turnover.

The final section of the civil law system is inheritance law, which regulates inheritance relations that arise in connection with the death of a citizen and the transfer of the deceased's property to his heirs.

The practical significance of the rule on the effect of civil legislation in time is reduced to several fundamental provisions:

a) If the legal acts generating, changing or terminating civil rights and obligations are defined differently by the new law than it was before the legal relationship arose, then the legality of such a legal relationship is assessed according to the legislation in force on the day of its occurrence;

b) A change in legislation does not automatically entail a change in civil legal relations, and they remain the same as they were at the time of their legal origin;

c) If the law prohibits the commission of any actions not previously prohibited, then such actions must be terminated.

These provisions serve as the content of the principle "the law has no retroactive effect".

But for relations in which, on the one hand, foreign legal entities are participants, on the other hand, a very important problem arises, which terminologically can be designated as the problem of "applicable law". Its solution boils down to finding out which state's law should be applied if a conflict situation has arisen in a legal relationship involving subjects of different states, and these relations are regulated differently by the legislation of different states. The correct resolution of the problem is of great practical importance, because disputes about the applicable law arise in legal relations with foreign investors or foreign partners under foreign economic contracts. The solution to the problem is based on the norms of a civil legal institution called private international law.

The applicable law is determined either directly by law or by contract. Law, as a rule, provides the applicable law for non-contractual legal relations. The norms of private international law, for example, provide that the law of the country of which he is a citizen determine the legal capacity of a foreign citizen, and the law of the country where the legal entity is established determines the legal capacity of foreign legal entities. The law of the country where the property is located determines the right of ownership of property, and the right of ownership of vehicles to be entered in state registers is determined by the law of the country where the vehicle is entered in the register.

Literatures:

1 Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany. Bonn, 2002. p. 32.

2 Constitutions of bourgeois states. Moscow, 1982. p. 281.

3 See: Universal Declaration of Human Rights of December 10, 1948 // Constitutional Law: Collection of constitutional and legal acts. Vol. 1. M., 1998. pp. 326-330.